

Historical Commentary / *Commentaire historique*

The ontogeny of the last Fermat's theorem

L'ontogénie du grand théorème de Fermat

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Abstract. This theorem well known has been studied in many ways since his publication. Nonetheless, the method of work that we have used is unique [7], which is in fact a meta-analysis, and guided us to find a classical proof by absurd. It also shows that Pierre de Fermat was right when he said to having the solution. Hence, it is sufficient to demonstrate that, if the proposition is true for one dimension, then it is true for all others. At the end, to extend this challenge that represented the resolution of the problem, we propose another one based on conception and elaboration of informative tools, actual and future.

Résumé. Ce théorème bien connu a été étudié de diverses façons depuis sa parution. Toutefois, la méthode de travail que nous avons utilisée est unique à plusieurs égards. Il s'agit en fait d'une méta-analyse, laquelle nous a guidé vers une solution classique, soit une preuve par l'absurde. Elle défend l'affirmation de Pierre de Fermat qui disait la connaître. Puisque il suffit de démontrer que la proposition soit vraie pour une dimension, pour montrer que cela s'applique à toutes les autres. À la fin, dans le but d'étendre ce défi que représentait la résolution du problème, nous en proposons un plus complexe. Celui-là faisant appel à la conception et l'élaboration d'outils informatifs actuels et futurs.

Keywords. Geometry, object, class, equivalence, inference, rule.

Mots-clés. Géométrie, objet, classe, équivalence, inférence, règle.

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Note. Following the rewards of 1857 and 1995.

1. Introduction

We recognize that the historical and individual growth of living pass by stages of pseudo-random development, guided by hereditary and genetical rules which tend to change slowly, but surely. The fact to say that species evolve themselves according to their environment is true, but there are exceptions. The best example is the humans vs cephalopods, reptiles or chimpanzees (in the past also called troglodytes) where those are stayed the same since their origins. The question is not to know how or why, but to discuss of more deterministic notions. We could also say that kind of theory, without to be totally true, neither totally false, has the merit to initiate reflexions and, with chances, inspire more universal theories. The subject of this article is a good example that in mathematics, we can define all things as objects having a certain life duration, but also they can renew themselves constantly.

Theorem 1. *There is no integer solution for the equation $X^n + Y^n = Z^n$; when X , Y , and Z are positive and not null integers; and n is greater then two [9].*

The data obtained show that the problem is mainly logical, instead of arithmetical. This is why we'll have many difficulties to solve it, if the strategy adopted is not the right one. Like in chess, or any competitive environment, to adapt itself and change of approach is often what it is the best to do, in realizing that we are in front of an obstacle apparently unsurmountable... About other results: successful or not, they served for the progression of many domains in sciences.

2. Preliminary study

2.1. Geometry

Let us recall that the physical construction must be perfect; id est all sides must be equal and whole. However...

Examples 2. Comparison of cubes.

Figure 1. $X = 1$ and $Y = 1$. $Z \approx 1,26$.

Figure 2. $X = 2$ and $Y = 1$.

Regardless other trials, suppose by example that X and Y were real numbers, Z^3 would be difficult to draw. Some unities must be divided or added to be organized adequately. Finally, if we wanted absolutely that Z^3 become the result of X^3 and Y^3 , by different conceptions, we would get more pronounced inequalities.

2.2. Functional analysis

Definition 3. Let $g^{1/n}(A) = \sqrt[n]{X^n + Y^n (= A)}$, be *Grouping*
 $r^{1/n}(B) = \sqrt[n]{Z^n (= B)}$, a *Resolution*
 $f_g(A) = \sqrt[n]{X^3 X^{n-3} + Y^3 Y^{n-3}}$ and $\sqrt[n]{Z^3 Z^{n-3}} = f_r(B)$, a *Tridimensionality*

Remarks 4.

- Thus we consider the images f_g of degree $n \geq 3$ are the result of grouped *cubes*. This means that $X^n + Y^n$ is a form A of which the image is not necessarily whole or congruent (but instead non-integer [cf. subsection 2.1]). All is seen as a space of cubical objects.
- f_g and f_r are *discrete functions* : i.e. they do not have continuous curve in plan, since they are made from integers.
- To define an appropriate function of comparison C_s , it could be interesting to view an image F as a species of structure (cf. [1]) that can be derived from a whole graph. Each edge would be a degree of a congruent form. A label I would correspond to an integer value of a representing side. This could also refer to a *theory of objects*, which is like molecular development (more details at the subsection 6.1)...

Figure 3. Cubes converted in special structures for a function C_s .

Remark 5. At Figure 1 and Figure 2, we add odd numbers to even numbers in trying to represent all integers. The differences obtained are reproduced when we increase these unities at superior dimensions. The inequalities always increase, as well. Think also that to compare arithmetical rules against one, $[x +]$ vs $[x]$, is the main reason why f_g et f_r are never equal.

2.3. *Direction change*

Question 6. *Let us verify the case $X = 8, Y = 9$ and $Z = 10$: it might have an intersection (with f_g and f_r [by increasing them vertically]), but it would be a real point. Even so, how to be sure that these false points are never whole numbers? We will answer to this question in the next sections.*

3. Experimental data

3.1. Simulation

Here is a function α_n , the cartesian product of trinomials (X^n, Y^n, Z^n) :

```

For n=3 to N; i = 16n-3
  For x=1 to L
    For y=1 to L
      For z=3 to 2L
        If (z ≠ x) and (z ≠ y) and Not (x = y = 1) and
          (zn ≥ xn + yn - i) and (zn ≤ xn + yn + i) and
          Not ((yn, xn) ∈ {E})
          Insert (xn, yn) into {E}
          Write x, y, xn + yn, z, zn, |Δγn|.
        End // If
      End // z
    End // y
  End // x
End // n
    
```

We then obtain these summary results¹:

X	Y	$X^3 + Y^3$	Z	Z^3	X	Y	$X^6 + Y^6$	Z	Z^6
6	8	728	9	729	1	2	65	3	729
9	10	1729	12	1728	...				
...							...		
566	823	738763263	904	738763264	3	3		...	
$0 \leq \Delta\gamma^3 \leq 1$					$0 \leq \Delta\gamma^6 \leq 4096$				
		$X^4 + Y^4$		Z^4			$X^7 + Y^7$		Z^7
					1	2	129	3	2187
					...				
					3	5	...		
$0 \leq \Delta\gamma^4 \leq 16$					$0 \leq \Delta\gamma^7 \leq 65536$				
					[...]				
		$X^5 + Y^5$		Z^5			$X^{366} + Y^{366}$		Z^{366}
1	2	33	3	243	1	2	15...65 [111 d.]	3	42...29 [175 d.]
...					...				
					...				
13	16				15	...			
$0 \leq \Delta\gamma^5 \leq 256$					$0 \leq \Delta\gamma^{366} \leq 12...96 [438 \text{ digits}]$				

Table 1. Samples of a programmed combinatoric.

¹The program is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/...>

In a few words: a calculation of absolute distances is done to evaluate if there is (by hazard) an equality between A and B. $N = 366$ is an intermediate exponent; and $L = 1000$ a sufficient number of integers for the variables x , y and z . After hours of processing, we verify that the distances become to high to form congruent images (*cf.* Table 1).

In analyzing the generated data, we observe that candidate integers x , y and z , those that we can see (because the measure is very large [16^{n-3}]), are less than 16. The set $E = \{\gamma^n\}$ is composed of solutions that diverge significantly when $n > 3$. Which is not always the case when we evaluate a sample with $n = 3$ (the maximum integer is then of order L).

Remark 7. It is not possible to create a perfect cube from two others considering the initial conditions and these results².

4. Conversion

E is the union of comparable images, for each combination of values x , y z and n . Still the definition has the default to miss efficiency. Even if there is no constraint of space and time, it must resemble as much as possible to the function α_n . For this, we introduce the notion of *selective combinatorics*. It is in fact a translation of the algorithm in a reusable formula for application, a starting model that we could complexify. Obviously, it depends of the context and the problems to solve.

4.1. Formalism

Definition 8. $\gamma^n = (X^n, Y^n, Z^n)$ is a class of Fermat.

Definition 9. $\Delta\gamma^n = (X^n + Y^n - Z^n)$ is the distance (scope) of a class of degree n .

Definition 10. The symbol \cup used means to add a class γ^n (or a suite) at the existing, if it is not already in the list.

Definition 11. The partial identity of a class is determined by the binomial (X^n, Y^n) , which is equal to another (Y^n, X^n) with the same values, but where the positions have been changed. Also, the symbol F_r is a function of unions.

Definition 12. We will note equally that $(\gamma^n)_{i-1}$ is the previous class of the current $(\gamma^n)_i$.

4.2. Movement

Definition 13. Let d be the direction as $d(\gamma^n) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \Delta\gamma^n > 0; \\ 0 & \text{if } \Delta\gamma^n = 0; \\ -1 & \text{if } \Delta\gamma^n < 0. \end{cases}$

- . $d(\gamma^n)_i \neq d(\gamma^n)_{i-1}$ is a direction change: when the current is positive and the previous is negative, or inversely; or if $d(\gamma^n) = 0$.
- . Most of suites are infinite, while some are not: a flag at the beginning of each suite permits to distinguish them. By default, it is unlimited (0); otherwise, it is a finite suite (1) determined by a direction change.

Definition 14. The operation $[E_{nd}]$ stops the current iteration when building a suite. Then the associated flag is set to 1.

²It is not a real proof but it guides to find a right one.

4.3. Expression

In the following enumerations, we will verify that a new suite begins each time there is a direction change.

- The current iterative index is incremented by 1; and v restarts to 1. The rest is useless for the proof, because these classes belong to a category of comparison already dealt with, or irrelevant.
- The classes with X or Y greater than or equal to Z are excluded, for obvious reasons.
- A class with the same identity as another will be ignored. Id est, duplicated values are not permitted.
- The limit of m tends to the infinite (∞); and $v = 2m$ could be better, however we want to keep a certain simplicity. We might say: it's not more effective, but in this study, there is no theoretical constraint of performance. And we can improve it eventually at the implementation phase. So we can imagine that all suites are consulted instantly...

t	u	\mathbb{F}
2	1	$\{1, (2^3, 1^3, 3^3)\},$
	2	$\{1, (2^3, 2^3, 3^3)\},$
	3	$\{1, (2^3, 3^3, 4^3)\},$
	...	$\cup\{\dots\},$
	m	$\{1, (\dots, (2^3, m^3, (2m)^3)\},$
3	1	$\{1, (3^3, 1^3, 4^3)\},$
	2	$\{\}$ this suite is already in the list,
	3	$\{1, (3^3, 3^3, 5^3)\},$
	...	$\cup\{\dots\},$
	m	$\{1, (\dots, (3^3, m^3, (2m)^3)\},$
		$\cup\{\dots\},$
m	1	$\{0 \mid 1, (\dots, (m^n, 1^n, q^n)\},$
	2	$\{0 \mid 1, (\dots, (m^n, 2^n, r^n)\},$
	3	$\{0 \mid 1, (\dots, (m^n, 3^n, s^n)\},$
	...	$\cup\{\dots\},$
	m	$\{0 \mid 1, (\dots, (m^n, m^n, (2m)^n)\}$

Table 2. Example of unions of suites γ^n .

Definition 15. *The synthesis of this combinatoric³ is as follows:*

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma^n(t, u, v) &= \{\gamma^n \mid X = t, Y = u, Z = v; \text{ and } m, n, t, u, v \in \mathbb{N}_{>0}\}, \text{ a singleton.} \\
 Fr(n, t, u) &= \begin{cases} \cup_{v=1}^{2m} \gamma^n(t, u, v) & \left[\begin{array}{l} \text{if } t < v \text{ and } u < v; \\ [End] \text{ if } d(\gamma^n)_v \neq d(\gamma^n)_{v-1}. \end{array} \right. \\ Fr(n, t) = \{Fr(n, t, u) \mid 1 \leq u \leq m\} \\ Fr(n) = \{Fr(n, t) \mid 1 \leq t \leq m\} \\ \mathbb{F} = \{Fr(n) \mid n \in \mathbb{N}_{\geq 3}\}. \end{cases} \tag{1}
 \end{aligned}$$

³Note that all serial mathematical functions like summations, products and integrals are iterative. The difference is that most of them have an end condition determined by an index having reached an upper bound (when it is not infinite). It's even more complicated with differentials [2]. Also, certain proofs are not necessarily entirely algebraic. For example, the one for $\sum_{i=1}^n i = (n(n+1))/2$ is visual, constructive, arithmetical and logical.

5. Homeostatic analysis

Definition 16. Let R the relation in F :

$\text{mod } R =$	1 if $\Delta\gamma^n > 0$ 0 if $\Delta\gamma^n = 0$ -1 if $\Delta\gamma^n < 0$	The classes γ are compared, either * horizontally, by increasing x, y and z ; or * vertically, by increasing n .
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Example 17. This sample shows how the classes progress when they change vertically.

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\gamma^n(6, 7, 8) &= (3,47), (4,-399), (5,-8185), (6,-97839), \dots \\
 |\gamma^n(7, 8, 9) &= (3,126), (4,-64), (5,-9474), (6,-151648), \dots \\
 |\gamma^n(10,20,30) &= (3,-18000), (4,-640000), (5,-21000000), (6,-664000000), \dots \\
 |\gamma^n(29,30,31) &= (3,21598), (4,593760), (5,16181998), (6,436319640), \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

The class $|\gamma^n(7, 8, 9)$ is an exception: there is an absolute decrease before (and at) the direction change (but not exactly if we exclude this result); and after, an increase. Given that theorem has been proven for $n \leq 6$, it not necessary to do something different only for this case. As we have seen, the comparison function is the absolute value of $\Delta\gamma^n$; and it is enough to determine that each progression is positive and exponential (by definition). Otherwise, we could delegate this task to a special function (cf Figure 3).

Proof.

(1) We want to verify that the set of null distances is empty:

Definition 18. Let $F_{\delta 0}^N$ be equal to $\{\gamma^j \mid \Delta\gamma^n = 0, \text{ where } 1 \leq j \leq N \text{ and } n = j + 2\}$.

It is known that all the distances $\Delta\gamma^3$ are not null; thus $F_{\delta 0}^1$ is empty (cf. [3]). If it was the case with N , would it be equally with $N + 1$?

Let us take all classes F . By the exponents rules and the constitution of this set, we deduce that each class has equivalences in other dimensions. Otherwise, there is no possible solution following an initial exclusion.

We can specify the image of $A = X^N + Y^N$ and $B = Z^N$ with two integers such that $e_i < \sqrt[N]{A} < \sqrt[N]{B} = Z = e_{i+1}$ (or inverse the inequality). By definition we have a sorted metric $[e_i, e_{i+1}]$ of which the absolute distances are growing and not null because $|A - B| > 0$ and $|e_i - e_{i+1}| > 0$. We have that $\forall x_j, x_{j+1} \in [e_i, e_{i+1}], x_{j+1} - x_j < \varepsilon$ et $x \in \mathbb{R} > 0$. $A - B \neq 0$.

For $N + 1$, we have also $\forall e_i, e_{i+1} \in \mathbb{N}^{N+1}, \exists \{Rt\} \in [e_i, e_{i+1}]$ such that $Rt \in \mathbb{R} > 0$. From where $A^{+1} - B^{+1} = AA^1 - BB^1 \neq 0$? This strategy renders difficult the resolution of the problem, because of the direction change that happens from a certain degree; but we do not know what it is. Moreover, we have $A^1 \neq B^1$: a smaller value against another could create an equality.

Logically, we can say that each time the classes are elevated at a degree $N + 1$, they grow proportionally in function of their previous values N respectively (they undergo a translation [cf subsection 2.2]). From the dimension $n = 4$, the images of A or B having a greater weight go farther each other (disymptotic functions). However, a visual proof will be correct only if it is accompanied from more precise objects like equations and their variables, for example. In the meantime, we prefer to find other alternatives.

(2) Propositional calculation:

Definition 19. *The operation \oplus is the passage from a dimension to another and consists to build cubes (pseudo-deformed) A and B (See the Figure 2).*

Definition 20. *By a circumstantial change of role, $\gamma^n(t, u, v) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \Delta\gamma^n = 0 \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases}$*

Definition 21. *Let $D_0^N = \sum_{j=1}^N \sum Fr(j+2)$ be the number of null distances.*

Does $D_0 = 0$? When $j = 1$, $D_0^1 = \sum Fr(3) = 0$. If it is true with N, let us verify for $N \oplus 1$. We have $D_0^{N \oplus 1} \leq D_0^N \oplus D_0^1$. For each term, we calculate the values true (1) or false (0) a number of times which is maximum $2m^3$. However, $\sum Fr(N+2) = 0$ and $\sum Fr(3) = 0$. It follows that the sum of null distances is zero because at best, we would get an equality; or a result less than 0, which is impossible. But is it enough to say that the searched solution does not exist?

(3) Now about the question 6: if it was the case, the intersection would be a whole number. In other word $g^{1/n} = r^{1/n}$ while $g^{1/(n-1)} \neq r^{1/(n-1)}$. The only possibility that an image would change of style, i.e. from real to integer, or from integer to real, is when there is a direction change, which causes an uncertainty. However, even if this hypothesis seems to be viable, at the same time, $A = (X^n + Y^n) \neq (X + Y)^n \gtrsim B$. In this context, there are two geometrical incompatible rules: grouping (g) and resolution (r) forms; although both must be satisfied.

Suppose that A was a whole form, then by hypothesis $A = B$. The image $g^{1/3}$ would be also whole because by definition, all the images (by g) of A would have the same integer value Z, whatever the dimension ($A^{1/n} = B^{1/n}$). In consequence, the contradiction derives from the fact that basically, $g^{1/3} \neq r^{1/3}$.

□

6. Conclusion

This case study amends the proof of Ernst Edward Kummer who has (partially) demonstrated the theorem for $n = 3$, $n = 5$, $n = 7$ and $n = 11$, notably; and Pierre de Fermat himself who has shown it for all n multiple of 4. The technique is like follows: instead of generalizing all from the beginning to the end, and after (by a deep analysis of images), we apply a simple logical rule of three. Also, the program written, a proof of concept, contributed to solve the problem only by observing the global form of data samples.

6.1. Suggestions of works

Although all this, if we refer to the previous section (1), we must admit that the number of strategies to solve this theorem is limited. With reason, because it is unusual that we can demonstrate a proposition in many ways. We often think to be at a detail to find a solution, to finally realize that these are unsuccessful tries. Do among hundreds of false proofs received at the *Académie des Sciences de Paris* [6], some were near to a solution, but have met similar difficulties? We could translate them in a normalized and readable format, create different scenarios and utilize an artificial intelligence software (to develop) [10], without capacity of learning (which is not always necessary to have), being more analytical: decomposition of articles in compact and simple matters...

As we verify, the multiplication of articles in this domain leads us to reflect on what should be done to improve their understanding and interest. One of the solutions would be to explore these subjects and categorize in distinct themes like:

Analysis Methods	Pedagogical language
Objects theory	Mathematical simulation

Table 3. Domains of study.

A classification of techniques of proofs would be certainly welcome. This could be found in a ISO standard. For example, compare the norm ISO 9001 (management of enterprises in general) to 80000 [5] to ascertain how the first is much more detailed than the second.

Other idea: there is in mathematics a theory of representation, but it does not seem to have one for the objects (otherwise, not enough clear and explicit) like conception of objects in computer science. Briefly, a statement of method adapted to the third millenary would be also wishful. But we must insure ourself although these notes: it is a possible realization, not a subjective critique. Here is an example of a guide to elaborate:

Function	Variable	Constant	Theorem	Lemma	Corolary
Definition	Equation	Substitution	Resolution	Example	Contrary
Synonym	Deduction	Association	Induction	Transposition	Order
Construction	Structure	Rule	Proposition	Combination	Probability
Projection	Inclusion	Nominative	Determinative	Image	Precision
Evaluation	Experience	Animation	Comparison	Alternation	Limit
Dimension	Quantity	Hypothesis	Observation	Commutation	Assembly
Axiom	Truth	Conversion	Inversion	Clarification	Symbol
Designation	Period	Abstraction	Refinement	Memory	Category
Identity	Addition	Inheritance	Permutation	Reduction	Extraction
Convergence	Formula	Recursion	Factorization	Neutrality	Selection
Amplitude	Transition	Cancellation	Tactic	Calculation	Case
Integrity	Duration	Reciprocity	Measure	Hazard	Orientation
Generalization	Specialization	Reflection	Anticipation	Position	Attribute
Synthesis	Elevation	Division	Application	Set	Role
Continuity	Graphy	Inference	Frequency	Dependance	Base
Infinity	Multiplication	Adjustment	Uniqueness	Equality	Existence
Connection	Stability	Distribution	Hybridization	Change	Evolution

Table 4. Nomenclature of objects and actions.

Proposition 22. *Specify, conceive and develop an help decision system having access to knowledge databases, according to the content^A presented at Table 3 and Table 4.*

There is also in management what we call different levels of abstraction necessary to understand a text, according to knowledges of persons. However, this is not what we find at the reading of most research publications in mathematics. Jacques Labelle [4] said to prefer (at the end of his career) teach to search, because "to work a lot and produce an article consulted by ten readers" is not enough satisfying. Everybody would be agree with that. Actually, a professor know less what is done outside his speciality. During a session of study, he becomes a learner. A doctoral dissertation could by conceived, for example, as an architecture of an information sub-system [8]:

⁴Possible improvement to facilitate the reading: in \LaTeX , we can not add a letter in the middle of another (like \mathbb{F}). Either we have the bottom and/or the top. In waiting to get this feature (by the symbol & ?), we will often say that the notation is abusive (cf. 21).

by defining the components, services and functions in more cohesive manner. This would be subdivided in three segments: (a) abstract (b) suites of logical symbols (with descriptions and references) and (c) the usual content and his conclusion.

Proposition 23. *Given the initial conditions (cf. 1), there is no direction change after $n = 6$. Apply the same method: algorithm, analysis of data by comparing identities, and a macroscopical analysis. Validate, by judicious modifications, the definition 18.*

We obtain an answer early enough just by verifying with another simulation. The data show that is not the case; and there are even direction changes after $n = 11$. Hence, there is no invariant that would permit to identify some convincing equations. We can see the trials can be many, but again, do not give probative results. More details at <https://zenodo.org/records/...> The same address where this document find itself.

6.2. Declaration of interests

The author does not work for, advise, own shares in, or receive funds from any organization that could benefit from this article, and declare to have no affiliation with a research organism. He is an independant searcher, not a professor at the University of Quebec. The address mentioned in page one is for the correspondance, and is only to conform with editor requirements.

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